

1 **LPS signaling in neonates.**

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7 We measured the total transcriptional response to lipopolysaccharide (LPS) at one hour, in neonates and
8 in adults to study LPS signaling in neonates. Monocytes from neonates produced *Cxcl5* rather than *Cxcl10*
9 and expressed *Cxcr1*. Neonatal monocytes expressed *Cd93* in response to LPS rather than *Cd69*.
10 Neonates selectively produced *Il1rap* in response to LPS. *Tfpi2* was induced in the immune cells of
11 neonates following exposure to LPS, as was *St18*. We describe specific induction of *Flvcr2* in neonatal
12 monocytes in response to LPS.

13 Citations

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